

**PRE-COMPETITION PREPARATION OF 10-12 YEAR OLD AMATEUR
JUDOKAS BASED ON THE APPLICATION OF MESOCYCLES AIMED AT
LOAD SELECTION.**

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Abstract: The relevance of the problem under study is determined by the extremely important significance of the rational design and implementation of the pre-competition training stage, which determines the level of sports achievements of amateur athletes in the main competitions of the season. A model of a two-month pre-competition training program for young judokas aged 10-12 was developed and tested. This model is based on the use of targeted mesocycles of total loads. The introduction of the experimental program into the training process ensured a significant increase in the level of general and special physical preparedness of athletes.

Keywords: young athletes, pre-competition training, training mesocycles, selective load orientation, general and special physical training.

Introduction; The theory and methodology of wrestling demonstrate a close relationship between the pre-competition preparation of young amateur judokas for the main competitions of the season and the effectiveness of their participation [1].

At the same time, the analysis of scientific and methodological literature shows that insufficient attention is paid to the issues of sports training related to the rational organization of training loads at the pre-competition training stage. The research currently lacks scientifically substantiated data on the effective structure and content of the training process for preparing young judokas for participation in competitive activities in accordance with the requirements of modern competitive practice of the strongest athletes [5].

In this regard, the chosen area of research aimed at searching for new directions in the organization and construction of the pre-competition training process of 10-12 year old judokas in order to improve the results of competitions is relevant and in demand practice.

The purpose of the research is to substantiate the rational design of the pre-competition stage of training and preparation of qualified 10-12 year old amateur judokas based on

the use of mesocycles that selectively direct training loads.

Methodology for organizing and conducting research

Two groups (control and experimental) of athletes engaged in judo wrestling in children's and youth sports schools of the city of Nukus participated in the research work, 28 people each. According to typological characteristics (age, training experience, qualifications, body weight, level of functional preparedness), the selection of young athletes in the experimental groups was the same. The age of the examined wrestlers was 10-12 years.

The pedagogical experiment was conducted under the natural conditions of the annual training cycle, in which the subjects carried out different content of pre-competition training. The training process of the athletes in the control group was carried out according to the traditional method in accordance with the judo curriculum for supplementary educational institutions [4]. Its essence was that 2-3 weeks before the important competitions, the total volume of training work performed during the competition period significantly decreased. The peculiarity of the pre-competition training of the athletes of the experimental group was that they trained according to a developed four-month program, consisting of current (long-term) and operational (short-term) stages, based on the use of training mesocycles with selective orientation of the total load [2].

In the process of pre-competition training of young judokas aged 10-12 in the experimental group, we identified the following methodological conditions, the implementation of which was carried out in a mandatory manner:

At the stages of pre-competition preparation, the systematic alternation of training loads was actively used. Volumetric or intensive training tasks were replaced by different selective directions of their influence;

At the current stage of pre-competition training, "sharp," concentrated loads in the form of shock microcycles, aimed at improving the basic physical qualities and abilities of a judoka, ensuring high performance in competitions, were widely used;

In order to increase the reliability of the implementation of the technical and tactical skills of athletes at the operational stage of pre-competition training, the volume of competitive matches has significantly increased.

In the first mesocycle of the current stage, basic aerobic training of judokas was carried out. Along with this, efforts were made to improve the speed-strength abilities and technical-tactical skills of athletes. In this mesocycle, the total volume of aerobic loads was in the range of 48% of the total volume of work performed, aerobic-anaerobic - 9%, speed-strength - 26%, and anaerobic-lactate - 17%.

Taking into account the competitive activity of young judokas, performed mainly in conditions of submaximal and maximum intensity, the subsequent programs of the average training cycles of the current stage of pre-competition training are aimed at solving the tasks of increasing the level of special endurance for work in anaerobic conditions.

In the second mesocycle, in aerobic-anaerobic work, 49% of the total load, aerobic - 17%, speed-strength - 30%, and anaerobic-lactate - 4% were allocated.

Within the third mesocycle of the average training cycle, the volume of work in the anaerobic-glycolytic, speed-strength, and anaerobic-alactatic directions was 54.9 and 6% of the total load for one mesocycle, and the volume of work in the aerobic and aerobic-anaerobic directions was 24 and 6%, respectively.

At the accelerated stage of pre-competition training (fourth mesocycle), work was carried out with a predominance of anaerobic-alactatic loads. Their total volume has reached 40%. Loads aimed at improving aerobic, aerobic-anaerobic, anaerobic-glycolytic, and speed-strength work capacity were allocated, respectively, 19, 9, 14, and 18% of the total volume of work performed.

The characteristics of the influence of experimental loads used at the pre-competition stages were assessed by the results achieved in the general and special physical training of athletes. Determination of the level of preparedness was carried out using a set of tests that allowed diagnosing the level of development of motor abilities, which is the first level for judokas. The following were used as indicators of general physical fitness: jump on a rope in 12 seconds (times); two-time push-off long jump from a standing position through a 2-meter zone in 25 seconds (times); gymnastics complex in 50 seconds (times). The indicators of special physical preparedness were assessed according to the data of the following tests: additional stride through the meter zone (times) in 12 seconds; turning the partner to a convenient side (times) in 25 seconds; technical complex (times) in 50 seconds [6].

Research results and their discussion

The obtained data indicate that as a result of the pre-competition training of young judokas of both control groups, positive changes occurred in the level of general and special physical training. At the same time, the quantitative changes in the absolute increase of the studied indicators in the subjects of the control and experimental groups have differences.

According to the data of the control tests, a significant absolute increase in the results was revealed in the experimental group compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Analysis and assessment of the growth rates of the studied physical fitness indicators

also indicate a significant increase in them in the representatives of the experimental group.

Conclusion

Thus, the pre-competition training program of 10-12 year old judokas, based on the use of selectively oriented training mesocycles of training loads, proved to be very effective and, compared to the control group, contributed to a significant increase in the level of general and special physical preparedness of the athletes of the experimental group ($p < 0.05$).

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